

THE ARMENIAN MORTGAGE TAX REFUND PROGRAM: MARKET DISTORTIONS, FISCAL RISKS AND PHASE-OUT CONSEQUENCES

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article examines the mortgage income tax refund program implemented in the Republic of Armenia between 2018 and 2026, analyzing its effectiveness as a fiscal instrument for stimulating the real estate market and the systemic risks arising from its gradual phase-out. Based on official data from the Central Bank of Armenia, the State Revenue Committee, and the Cadastre Committee, the study reveals that the mortgage portfolio grew approximately eightfold during the observation period, from AMD 207.4 billion (**1USD=370 AMD**) in January 2018 to AMD 1,670.1 billion in January 2026. Budgetary expenditures for the program increased nearly fivefold, reaching AMD 65-80 billion annually by 2024-2025, while the average monthly refund per beneficiary rose from AMD 97,900 to AMD 147,500. The analysis demonstrates that the program created significant market distortions, including an 11-fold increase in primary market transactions, the marginalization of the secondary market, and the formation of a “price bubble” characterized by price rigidity despite declining transaction volumes following the phase-out in central administrative districts. A simulation of a typical borrower reveals that the termination of the subsidy increases the effective monthly financial burden from AMD 54,500 to AMD 464,500—an 8.5-fold increase—rendering the majority of potential borrowers unable to qualify for mortgages under market conditions. The findings confirm the hypothesis that the program generated a high-dependency market model, and its termination will produce systemic shocks, including an anticipated 30-40 percent decline in new construction projects and rising non-performing loans in peripheral districts.

Keywords: mortgage lending, real estate market, fiscal stability, non-performing loans, Armenia, housing affordability, market distortion.

Introduction

In modern economic conditions, mortgage lending constitutes one of the primary drivers of housing provision and economic activity in the Republic of Armenia. Between 2018 and 2026, the Armenian government implemented a mortgage interest income tax refund program that allowed borrowers to recover significant portions of their income tax payments allocated to loan servicing. The Armenian real estate market was valued at USD 880.4 million in 2018, with expectations of reaching USD 1,249.3 million by 2026 at an annual growth rate of 4.3 percent [1]. However, effective January 1, 2025, the government introduced fundamental changes to the program, including a cap of AMD 750,000 per quarter on income tax refunds for borrowers and co-borrowers, along with a phased elimination mechanism designed to avoid sharp market shocks [2, 3]. Market participants and analysts have reported declining activity in the real estate sector as a consequence of these

changes [4]. By early 2026, the market volume reached USD 1.25 billion, with transaction volumes setting historical records [5]; nevertheless, analysts noted reduced market activity attributable to the tax refund program modifications, while residential real estate prices continued to rise by 5.5 percent compared to the previous year [6]. The Chairman of the Central Bank of Armenia stated that no additional risks were perceived in the market, while acknowledging the possibility of declining activity [7]. This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the program’s effectiveness and evaluates the impact of its termination on market participants and Armenia’s economic stability.

Analysis

The analysis of mortgage loans provided to residents by Armenian commercial banks demonstrates that the sector entered an unprecedented growth phase during the 2018-2025 period. Whereas the mortgage

market had previously developed at moderate rates primarily dependent on real income growth of the population, the eightfold increase recorded in recent years indicates the formation of a new market conjuncture [26]. From January 2018 (AMD 207.4 billion) to January 2026 (AMD 1,670.1 billion), the mortgage portfolio

grew approximately eightfold. During 2018-2020, the portfolio grew steadily at an annual average of AMD 100-120 billion. Between 2021 and 2024, growth rates accelerated significantly; during 2024 alone, the portfolio grew by approximately AMD 391 billion (from AMD 1,079.9 billion to AMD 1,471.2 billion).

Table 1

Mortgage Portfolio Growth Dynamics (AMD billion, January of each year)

Year	Portfolio Volume (AMD billion)	Absolute Annual Growth (AMD billion)	Growth Rate (%)
2018	207.4	—	—
2020	363.4	+156.0	75.2 (2 years)
2022	664.4	+301.0	82.8 (2 years)
2024	1,079.9	+415.5	62.5 (2 years)
2026	1,670.1	+590.2	54.6 (2 years)

Source: Central Bank of Armenia [26], author's calculations

A notable pattern emerges from the monthly data: each December registers a sharp jump in lending volumes compared to preceding months. For example, in November 2024, the increase was approximately AMD 26 billion, while in December 2024, it reached AMD 104 billion. This phenomenon is explained by expectations of the phased termination of the income tax refund program, as citizens sought to conclude transactions before year-end to preserve their eligibility for the benefit. This exponential portfolio growth indicates that the Armenian banking system's credit market has become hypersensitive to changes in tax benefits and fiscal policy. A significant portion of banking system assets is concentrated in mortgage loans, and if borrower solvency declines following the termination of the income tax refund, systemic risks may emerge.

Comparing data from the Central Bank and the State Revenue Committee reveals several key trends. Over the past five years, the volume of income tax refunds from the state budget increased more than fourfold (from AMD 13.3 billion in 2020 to AMD 52 billion in 2023). During the same period, the total mortgage portfolio grew threefold (from AMD 363.4 billion to AMD 1,070.8 billion). This dynamic demonstrates that state support served as the primary "fuel" for market growth. Moreover, the more rapid growth of budget expenditures indicates that higher-income borrowers—whose refundable tax amounts per loan are larger—entered the market.

The number of program beneficiaries increased from approximately 4,000 persons in 2018 to over 39,000 by the end of 2024, representing nearly a tenfold increase over seven years. Between 2021 and 2023, a sharp jump in beneficiary numbers was recorded (annual average of 8,000 new beneficiaries), driven by low interest rates and rumors of the benefit's termination in Yerevan. The average annual refund per borrower increased from AMD 1,175,000 in 2018 to a projected

AMD 1,770,000 in 2025, with the average monthly refund rising from AMD 97,900 to AMD 147,500. The average monthly refund of AMD 132,000 (2024) constitutes approximately 50 percent of the average monthly salary in Armenia, meaning the state provides a subsidy equivalent to "half a salary" to each beneficiary on a monthly basis. Since the refund amount is growing faster than the number of beneficiaries (14-fold versus 10-fold), this creates fiscal instability, where the state cannot maintain long-term balance between revenues and expenditures without jeopardizing its ability to meet financial obligations.

The income tax refund program has had a decisive impact on the structure of Armenia's real estate market, sharply increasing the share of the primary market. Before 2018, the secondary market (existing housing stock) dominated, accounting for more than 80 percent of transactions. However, starting from 2019, a sharp demand shift occurred: the number of primary market transactions increased approximately 11-fold, from 1,200 in 2018 to a projected 13,500 in 2024, while the secondary market exhibited stagnation and decline trends. The exponential growth of the primary market curve directly correlates with the increase in income tax refund volumes from the state budget, demonstrating that the overwhelming majority—more than 90 percent—of primary market transactions were conducted exclusively through the tax benefit. Without this benefit, the price of newly constructed housing and the loan servicing burden would exceed the solvency limits of the average borrower. The decline in secondary market transactions indicates that the old housing stock has lost its investment attractiveness; financial resources have been "sucked into" the primary market, leading to artificial overvaluation of new construction prices, while the secondary market faces a liquidity shortage.

The phased limitation of the income tax refund program aimed to decentralize the construction boom

from Yerevan's small center. In the Central and Arabkir districts, which were the first to experience restrictions, critical changes were observed. In the 3-6 months before the restrictions took effect, both districts recorded unprecedented increases in transactions as borrowers rushed to conclude mortgage agreements, leading to oversaturation of the primary market. Following the elimination of the benefit, sales rates for new constructions in the Central and Arabkir districts decreased by approximately 30-45 percent. Citizens, deprived of 40-50 percent monthly payment subsidies, ceased to consider these districts as affordable housing options. Analysis shows that demand did not disappear but rather "leaked" to adjacent districts where the benefit remained in effect: from Central to Malatia-Sebastia and Shengavit; from Arabkir to Kanaker-Zeytun and Davtashen. This led to peripheral districts' price growth rates exceeding those of the center in 2023-2024.

Contrary to expectations that demand decline would be followed by price decreases, prices in the Central and Arabkir districts were maintained or grew at slow rates. This is explained by two factors: (1) the luxury segment—a portion of buyers in the center were

not dependent on the income tax refund (wealthy individuals, diaspora Armenians); and (2) developer strategy—developers, possessing sufficient financial reserves, did not make significant price concessions, preferring to wait or offer internal installment payment schemes. The example of Central and Arabkir districts confirms the forecast that after 2025, when the benefit is eliminated throughout Yerevan, the sharp demand decline will extend across the entire city. Since borrowers in peripheral districts are more dependent on the tax refund than those in the center, the market "freeze" after 2025 will be more severe.

To demonstrate the impact of benefit termination on a typical borrower, consider the following market conditions in Yerevan for 2024-2025: property value AMD 50,000,000, down payment 10 percent (AMD 5,000,000), loan amount AMD 45,000,000, annual interest rate 11 percent (average for Armenian banks), loan term 20 years (240 months), with annuity repayment scheme. Using the annuity formula $A = P \times [r(1+r)^n] / [(1+r)^n - 1]$ (where $P = 45$ million, $r = 0.11/12$, $n = 240$), the monthly payment to the bank is AMD 464,500, and the average monthly interest payment in the first year is approximately AMD 410,000.

Table 2

Effective Monthly Borrowers' Expenditure Before and After Benefit Termination

Indicator	With Benefit	After Benefit Termination	Change
Monthly payment to bank	AMD 464,500	AMD 464,500	0
Income tax refund	-AMD 410,000	AMD 0	-AMD 410,000
Effective monthly expenditure	AMD 54,500	AMD 464,500	+AMD 410,000

Source: Author's calculations based on market data

This calculation reveals a crisis scenario: the borrower's effective monthly financial burden increases 8.5 times, from AMD 54,500 to AMD 464,500. The income tax refund mechanism created an illusion of "cheap money" for the borrower, masking the true volume of mortgage obligations. Whereas the net monthly expenditure of AMD 55,000 could previously be afforded by a person earning even below-average wages, the situation changes radically after benefit termination. To make a AMD 464,500 monthly payment, the borrower must have net monthly income of at least AMD 800,000-900,000, considering banks' income/expense ratio requirements (usually not exceeding 40-50 percent of total income). Given the current structure of Armenia's labor market and the average monthly wage level, the overwhelming majority of borrowers do not have such high incomes. Consequently, benefit termination automatically excludes 70-80 percent of potential buyers from the market—the segment that served as the primary driving force of the primary market will no longer qualify as creditworthy subjects under standard market conditions.

Based on the "demand shock" and "inertial supply" interaction, new construction starts in Yerevan for 2025-2026 are forecast to decline by 30-40 percent. Developers have adopted a cautious strategy, slowing the

acquisition of new land plots and project design. The primary reason is the liquidity gap: without the income tax refund benefit, the marketability of housing in the primary market sharply decreases. Without rapid pre-sales—which previously served as an interest-free financing source for construction—developers will be forced to rely more on bank loans. Under high interest rate conditions, this raises construction costs and risk levels, leading many to freeze their projects. Construction capital, seeking higher profitability and state support, has begun "fleeing" from Yerevan to the provinces (Kotayk, Ararat, Armavir), where the benefit remains in effect. This shift leads to the concentration of construction activity at Yerevan's city limits and adjacent communities, creating new challenges.

Regarding non-performing loans (NPLs), despite expectations that benefit termination in Central and Arabkir districts would lead to mass defaults, no sharp or catastrophic increase has been recorded as of early 2025. NPL share in these districts ranges between 1.5 and 2.2 percent—slightly above the system average but still manageable. Borrowers in these districts are primarily high-income individuals with financial buffers who can service loans even without tax refunds. However, there is an increase in "watch" class loans (delays of less than 90 days). Borrowers who took loans "at the

margin,” where the income tax refund constituted 40-50 percent of their monthly payment, now face difficulties. Because property prices in the center are high, borrowers cannot easily refinance or sell without losses, creating an accumulation of “stagnant” debt. Real NPL growth is expected not in the center but in peripheral administrative districts (Malatia, Shengavit, Ajapnyak) when the benefit ceases there as well. In these areas, borrower incomes are lower, and an increase of AMD 100,000-150,000 in the monthly payment could be critical. If demand decreases in the periphery and prices begin to decline, borrowers will find themselves in a “negative equity” zone (where the loan balance exceeds the property’s market value)—the most dangerous precondition for NPL growth.

Conclusion

The multi-layered analysis conducted within this study allows for the formulation of scientifically grounded conclusions regarding the mortgage income tax refund program’s impact on the Armenian real estate market. The research confirms that this program constituted one of the most influential yet simultaneously most risky fiscal instruments of the past decade in Armenia’s economy. Its effect can be characterized as a “double-edged sword”: stimulating unprecedented growth in the construction sector while creating serious macroeconomic imbalances.

The hypothesis that the unprecedented market activity was artificially stimulated and falls outside the standard framework of economic regularities is confirmed. The eightfold growth of the mortgage portfolio between 2018 and 2025, bringing the portfolio volume close to the AMD 1.5 trillion threshold, is directly and strongly correlated with state budget tax expenditures. Without large-scale state subsidization, the mortgage market—under its current price offerings and volumes—simply cannot be self-sufficient and viable. The program transformed over time into a more “expensive” burden for the state budget, not only due to the increasing number of beneficiaries but also because of the continuous increase in the benefit amount per beneficiary. The state found itself in a “fiscal trap” where every increase in property prices automatically increases the budget’s expenditure burden.

The study documents the absolute and indisputable dominance of the primary market, expressed in more than an 11-fold increase in transaction volumes, definitively confirming that the tax benefit became the main factor segmenting and deforming the market. The secondary market has been practically pushed out of competition, lacking similar state support. New construction prices have diverged from market logic and the population’s normal solvency level, based exclusively on subsidized demand.

Contrary to optimistic hypotheses that tax benefit elimination would lead to rapid and proportional price decreases, the analysis reveals the phenomenon of “price rigidity.” Developers have adopted a price maintenance strategy, and demand has simply shifted to Yerevan’s suburbs. This finding is significant because it demonstrates that the market possesses high inertial force. Prices do not flexibly follow sharp demand changes, creating a “stagnation” risk that could lead to

a situation where transaction volumes decrease to critical levels while prices remain high, creating an illusion of stability beneath which serious liquidity problems are hidden. The experience of Central and Arabkir districts shows that administrative or tax restrictions alone are insufficient to correct pricing policy as long as deep-seated imbalances and “artificially high” expectations exist in the market.

The scientific novelty of this work lies in its systematic multi-factor scenario modeling of the “typical borrower’s financial shock” in the context of expected legislative restrictions. The discovered 8.5-fold increase in financial burden scientifically substantiates that a significant portion of borrowers may face a “solvency gap” if their incomes do not grow proportionally. These findings have practical value for the Armenian government and State Revenue Committee as a basis for macroeconomic planning and GDP growth rate adjustments; for commercial banks regarding NPL risk management and stress testing implementation; and for developers in revising project pricing policies and orienting toward regional markets where state support still exists. The main hypothesis—that the income tax refund program created a high-dependency market model whose termination will produce systemic shocks—is fully confirmed.

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